

Influence of fungicides on the production of pectinolytic enzymes of *R. solani*

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Sheath blight disease caused by
Rhizoctonia solani is serious in many

rice-growing areas of Tamil Nadu. The introduction of high yielding and fertilizer-responsive rice strains has intensified its occurrence and severity.

The influence of certain fungicides on enzyme inhibition was studied. Incorporation of Kitazin, Hinosan, Benlate, Bavistin, Daconil, Vitavax, Thiabendazole, and wettable ceresan in Czapek's Pectin medium markedly

inhibited the pathogen's growth. Kitazin inhibited the production of pectinolytic enzymes PC, PGTE, and PTE significantly. Inhibition of PTE production was maximum with Hinosan, and next highest with Bavistin. Both fungicides also inhibited PG and PGTE production considerably. □

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Laboratory evaluation of insecticides as foliar spray for control of the rice leaf folder

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The rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* is found throughout Asia but is most abundant in the tropics. Its importance has increased in recent years, possibly because of changes in cultural practices associated with improved rice technology. Because no variety with resistance to the leaf folder is available, insecticides are the only immediately practical and effective means of control.

Although most tropical Asian countries recommend chemical control of leaf folders, few recommendations are based on experimental data because of problems in conducting reliable field trials. A technique for mass rearing of leaf folder larvae was recently developed at IRRI. It will enable scientists to evaluate insecticides in the laboratory.

Taichung Native 1 seedlings of 25 to 30 days of age were infested with freshly hatched leaf folder larvae. When all the leaves had folded (about 2 weeks after infestation), the potted plants were sprayed with various test insecticides at 0.04% concentration. Two days later, the folded leaves were opened. The living and dead larvae were counted and the percentage of mortality was determined.

Most of the insecticides controlled the leaf folder adequately (see table). Among

Activity of insecticides applied as a 0.04% foliar spray on potted Taichung Native 1 plants infested with freshly hatched larvae of leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*. IRRI greenhouse, 1978.

Insecticide	formulation	Mean mortality (%) ^a
FMC 27289	48 EC	100 a
Permethrin	10 EC	100 a
Monocrotophos	16.8 EC	100 a
Cypermethrin	40 BC	98 ab
Miral	50 EC	98 ab
Chlorfenvinphos	20 EC	98 ab
Methyl parathion	50 EC	93 abc
BPMC	31.5 EC	90 bc
Carbofuran	12 F	90 bc
Endosulfan	35 EC	85 bc
FMC 35001	48 EC	83 bc
Azinphos ethyl	40 EC	83 bc
A47171	24 EC	75 bc
Propoxur	20 EC	73 c
Metalkamate	30 EC	33 d
MIPC	50 WP	23 de
Vamidothion	40 EC	13 de
Perthane	45 EC	5 e

^a With 10 larvae/replicate; average of 4 replications. Values adjusted using Abbott's formula. Means in the same column followed by the same letter do not differ at the 5% level of significance.

them were several new compounds — not yet commercially available — that were also found effective against the brown planthopper (BPH) in previous studies. Perthane, a selective compound that was highly effective against the BPH in previous tests, did not control the leaf folder. It also had little effect on stem borers in previous studies. □

Identification of insecticides that induce BPH resurgence when applied as granules to rice

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Resurgence of brown planthopper (BPH) populations after a brief period of reduction following rice crop protection with certain insecticides has been reported repeatedly at IRRI. Paddy-water application of gamma-BHC, diazinon, Sevidol, and Miral has caused BPH resurgence at IRRI. In India, granular formulations of phorate, diazinon, quinalphos, and mephosfolan had varying levels of effectiveness in the period after initial application, then induced BPH buildups at later growth stages.

In controlled studies at IRRI, the reproductive rate of BPH was higher when the insects were confined on plants treated with diazinon and cartap granules (see table). Plants protected with the two insecticides were also hopperburned earlier than the other treatments, after loss of insecticidal efficacy. Evidently, the increase in reproductive rate may be the primary factor causing BPH resurgence. The reduced BPH reproduction in plants treated with FMC 31768 is also significant when selecting the best insecticides for BPH control.

BPH reproduction was higher in plants that received 0.5 kg a.i./ha of five of the granules tested than in plants treated

with 1.0 kg a.i./ha (Cartap was an exception). That indicates impending BPH resurgence when low dosages of granular insecticides are applied to the rice crop (regardless of whether the low doses were due to economic limitations, defective distribution, or dilution by rains shortly after application). □

Identification of insecticides that induce brown planthopper resurgence when applied as foliar spray

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Field and insectary experiments at IRRI have consistently shown that foliar spraying of rice with insecticides such as methyl parathion, decamethrin, and diazinon induces brown planthopper (BPH) resurgence after the insecticide's toxicity is lost. Detailed studies of BPH resurgence by the authors revealed that the reproductive rate of BPH on plants protected with different insecticides would be an appropriate criterion in evaluating an insecticide's resurgence potential. Following this technique, 23 common emulsifiable concentrates of insecticides were evaluated under controlled conditions.

Among the four classes of insecticides tested, organophosphates and synthetic pyrethroids generally tended to cause resurgence, while carbamates and organochlorines were fairly safe (see table). But there were exceptions in both groups. Screening studies suggested that A 47171, FMC 35001, vamidothion, BPMC, and Perthane reduced the BPH reproductive rate significantly. Perthane, BPMC, and A 47171 have been identified as effective for BPH control in both laboratory and field experiments at IRRI. The fact that they do not cause resurgence may make them more important for BPH control. On the other hand, this evaluation also suggested that the use of methyl parathion, fenitrothion, decamethrin, diazinon, and fenthion should be avoided in BPH-infested areas because they stimulate BPH reproduction. □

Reproduction of and damage by brown planthopper as influenced by type and rate of granular insecticides applied to potted rice plants.^a

Treatment ^b	Insecticide rate (kg a.i./ha)	Nymphs ^c (no.)	No. of days for complete hopperburning ^d
Diazinon	1.0	305.3 b	16.0 bc
Diazinon	0.5	379.3 a	14.0 abc
Cartap	1.0	388.7 a	13.7 ab
Cartap	0.5	249.0 bcd	11.0 a
Aldicarb	1.0	202.7 de	17.7 cd
Aldicarb	0.5	316.7 ab	15.3 bc
Dacamox	1.0	247.0 bcd	24.7 fg
Dacamox	0.5	277.7 bc	23.3 efg
Carbofuran	1.0	189.7 d	26.7 g
Carbofuran	0.5	213.7 cd	24.7 fg
FMC 31768	1.0	137.7 e	25.0 fg
FMC 31768	0.5	187.3 d	22.7 ef
Control	—	234.7 cd	20.7 de

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^b Granules were incorporated into the soil twice when the plants were 35 and 47 days old.

^c From eggs laid by 2 females/7 days, 30 days after second application of granules.

^d Damage by nymphs that emerged from eggs laid by 2 females. Days from the emergence of first group of nymphs.

Reproductive rate of brown planthopper as influenced by various insecticides applied as foliar spray on rice. IRRI, 1978.

Treatment ^a	Formulation EC (%)	Class ^b	Reproductive rate ^c (no. of nymphs)
A47171	24	OP	107.0 a
FMC 35001	48	C	115.3 a
Vamidothion	40	OP	116.7 a
BPMC	50	C	120.0 a
Perthane	45	OC	124.7 a
Carbophenothion	40	OP	135.0 ab
FMC 27289	48	C	155.7 abc
FMC 31768	23	C	161.0 abc
Endosulfan	35	OC	182.3 abcd
Control (water spray)	—	—	207.3 bcde
Acephate	40	OP	210.7 bcde
Phosphamidon	50	OP	211.3 bcde
Methomyl	19.3	C	214.0 cde
Azinphos ethyl	40	OP	236.7 def
AC 64475	25	OP	252.3 defg
Dacamox	23	OP	253.3 efg
Cypermethrin	40	P	255.7 efg
Triazophos	40	OP	262.7 efg
Monocrotophos	16.8	OP	269.0 efg
Methyl parathion	50	OP	297.0 fghij
Fenitrothion	20	OP	322.0 ghij
Decamethrin	2.5	P	334.7 hij
Diazinon	20	OP	336.0 ij
Fenthion	50	OP	353.0 j

^a Insecticides applied as a foliar spray 3 times on plants at 20-, 30-, and 40-days after sowing at 0.04% concentration except cypermethrin and decamethrin, which were sprayed at 0.00270 concentration.

^b C = carbamate, OC = organochlorine, OP = organophosphate, P = pyrethroid.

^c From eggs laid by 2 females/7 days. The females were released 30 days after the third spraying. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.